

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	Gabú Project
				Min: 62.479 Max: 62.846	1390 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 2134-2137 Photo Model: Yes No #: 332

DEFINITION: Wall Southernmost room N° 6

Covered by SU: 1327 Fills SU: 1441 Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abuted by: 1470, 1448, 1449, 1393	Abuts: 1415
Is covered by: 1327, 1450	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts: 1468
Is filled by:	Fills: 1441

OBSERVATIONS: Dry conditions, excavation by pickaxe & trowel to find patchy structure

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: southwestern, near corner; perpendicular to 'Via Claudia'

Shape: linear wall structure shape, very straight

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): gentle slope east

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: east-west

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size: Small (range) 10-15 Medium (range) 20-40 Large (range) 40-50 Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz
cm cm cm

Wall Facing: Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

l = 830 cm, w = 63 cm

Description:
Wall made of unworked Tufo block, southernmost wall of the structure.

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

sorry! see sketch on front

INTERPRETATION

It abuts a thicker wall on the western side. This thicker wall appears to be of a later construction since it does not align. For that reason, SU 1390 likely the southernmost wall of the structure. 1396 also appears to be bound to a north-south wall which is partially covered by a tufo floor (SU 1396).

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	<u>AMB, Jacob Kovacs</u>	on	<u>15.07.2011, 20/7/11</u>
Revised by	<u>CHM</u>	on	<u>1.8.2011</u>
PDFd by	<u>ELR</u>	on	<u>3.8.11</u>
Entered by		on	